

macerated testis and the testis is pressed through blotting paper to ensure adequate spread of the cells. Moderate pressure can be applied with a blunt pencil eraser to flatten the cells. The slide is examined under high magnification of a light microscope to ascertain if cells have spread and if the stain has been absorbed by cell nuclei. Extra stain can be removed by adding a few drops of 45% acetic acid on one side of the cover slip and withdrawing the excess fluid from the opposite side using an absorbent.

The preparation is passed over an alcohol lamp flame 3 to 4 times to hasten destaining and to clear the cytoplasm.

A temporary mount is maintained by sealing or ringing the cover slip with paraffin wax. For a permanent mount, the paraffin seal is carefully removed with xylene and the slide subjected to 95% alcohol for 5 minutes, 70% alcohol for 5 minutes, xylene for 5 minutes, and xylene for another 5 minutes. The cover slip is then removed and a drop of Canada balsam is put on the spot where the cover slip came. A new cover slip is

Meiotic chromosomes of brown planthopper biotype 1 males. a. Late diakinesis or prometaphase I chromosomes. b. Metaphase I chromosomes in testicular cells, IRRI, 1981.

placed on the preparation. The removed cover slip receives another drop of Canada balsam and is placed on the left side of the glass slide. The prepared slide is dried on a slide warmer and cleaned with xylene.

Mounted slides are labeled on the right side with specimen identification, stage of cell division, date of preparation, and worker's name.

3. Detection of M-phase — Physical and metabolic activities of growing cells are cyclic, characterized by four more or less distinct stages — G1-, S-,

G2-, and M-phases — which are regular and repetitive as long as a cell is growing and dividing. Chromosomes undergoing different meiotic stages are detected during the M-phase, which usually lasts an hour. The specific M-phase for brachypterous 5th-instar and newly emerged males of brown planthopper biotype 1 was 0700-0800 h, after which a majority of the sex cells were observed to undergo interphase or active metabolic phases (G1-, S-, and G2-phases) (see figure). ■

Distribution, seasonal occurrence, and natural enemies of armyworm attacking rice in China

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Eight noctuid species of rice armyworm belonging to two genera, *Mythimna* and *Spodoptera*, are found in China:

Mythimna separata (Walker), *M. loreyi* (Duponchel), *M. compta* (Moore), *M. zaeae* (Duponchel), *Spodoptera maurifaria* Boisduval, *S. depravata* (Butler), *S. abyssinia* Guenée, and *S. pecten* Guenée. *M. separata* is the most important.

The oriental armyworm *Mythimna separata* (Walker) has been recorded from Hianan Island of Kwangtung Province to Heilungkiang Province.

South of latitude 33° N (January iso-

therm 0° C), *M. separata* can hibernate in winter (see table). Between 27 and 33° N, larvae generally overwinter with pupae. Sometimes they feed lightly on cereal plants, but the rate of development is slow. South of 27° N (January isotherm 80° C), it infests wheat severely in winter.

Parasites and predators include Tachinidae [*Cuphocera varia* (Fabricius), *Linnaemya compta* (Fallen), *L. zachvatkini* Zimin, *Servillia planifor-*

ceps Chao, *Siphona cristata* Fabricius, *Actia silacea* Meigen, *Exorista japonica* (Townsend), *E. fallax* Meigen, *Bessa selecta frugax* Rondani, *Carcelia excisa* (Fallen), *Drino inconspicua* Meigen, *Pales pavida* Meigen, *Pseudogonia rufifrons* (Wiedemann), *Turanogonia chinensis* (Wiedemann)], Braconidae [*Apanteles ruficrus* (Haliday), *Meteorus sp.*], Ichneumonidae [*Charops bicolor* Szepliget, *Vulgichneumon leucaniae* Uchida, *Camposcopus* sp., *Netelia* sp.],

Number of generations and seasonal occurrence of *Mythimna separata* in China.

Generations per year	Seasonal occurrence	Host plants	Latitude
2-3	Jun-Jul	Wheat, maize, rice, sorghum, millet	North of 39° N
3-4	Jul-Aug	Wheat, maize, rice, sorghum, millet	36-29° N
4-5	Apr-May	Wheat, maize, rice, millet	33-36° N
5-6	Sep-Oct	Rice, maize	27-33° N
6-7	Mar-Apr	Wheat	South of 27° N
	Jan-Apr	Wheat	
	Sep-Oct	Rice, maize, sugarcane	

Scelionidae [*Telenomus cirphivorus* Liu.], and Carabidae [*Calathus halensis* Schall., *Calosoma maderae chinense* Kirby].

Seasonal migration in eastern China was traced by releasing and recapturing marked moths. Results indicate that the moth is a regular immigrant from the southern provinces to the northeast in early spring. A return migration takes place in late summer or fall.

The maize armyworm *Mythimna loreyi* Duponchel is found in Chekiang, Kiangsu, Kwangtung, Kwangsi, Fukien, Hunan, Hupeh, Szechuan, Kweichow, Kiangsi, Taiwan, and Ginsu Provinces. In Kwangtung, it damages rice in June-July by feeding on the leaves and cutting the spikelets. Parasites of *M. loreyi* include Tachinidae [*Cuphocera varia* Fabricius, *Pseudogonia rufifrons* (Wied.)], Braconidae [*Apanteles* sp.], and Ichneumonidae [*Enicospilus* sp.].

The grain armyworm *Mythimna compta* (Moore) is found in Hupeh, Hunan, Kiangsi, Yunan, Fukien, Chekiang, Kweichow, Kwangtung, and Kwangsi Provinces. In Fukien, it causes significant injury in June-July during its second generation and serious damage in October-November during its fifth generation. In Kwangtung, its infestation on rice is lighter than other species.

The millet armyworm *Mythimna zea* (Duponchel) infests wheat, millet, and rice in Sinkiang Province in the west-northern part of China. It produces two generations a year and the full-grown larva hibernates in the soil. The first generation in June-July causes significant damage.

The nutgrass armyworm *Spodoptera mauritia* Boisduval is found in Kiangsu, Hupeh, Kiangsi, Kwangsi, Kwangtung, Taiwan, and Fukien Provinces. Caterpil-

lars of the 5th generation attack rice severely in Kwangtung in July-August. It often occurs in rice fields that are easily flooded. An outbreak is closely related to water in the fields.

The small nutgrass armyworm *Spodoptera abyssinia* Guenée occurs in Hunan, Fukien, Kwangsi, and Kwangtung Provinces. The caterpillars infest rice seedlings during the second season in June-July in Kwangtung. The duration of the summer generation lasts about 33 days in Guangzhou.

The green nutgrass armyworm *Spodoptera depravata* (Butler) is found in Giling, Shensi, Hupeh, Kiangsi, Szechuan, Chekiang, Kiangsu, Fukien, and Kwangtung Provinces.

The striped nutgrass armyworm *Spodoptera pecten* Guenée occasionally infests rice in Fukien, Kwangtung, and Kwangsi Provinces. ■

Weed hosts of some rice pests in North Western Sierra Leone

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Grasses in the rice fields of associated tidal mangrove swamps of Mawirr and Magbolontor and the mangrove swamp of the Rice Research Station in Rokupr, Kambi District, North Western Sierra Leone, were examined for adults, eggs, larvae, and nymphs of rice insect pests (see table). Insects at immature stages were reared to adults for identification. ■

Distribution of some rice insects on weeds in North Western Sierra Leone.

Insect	Insect stage	Site	Weed host	Rice crop stage
<i>Diopsis thoracica</i> West.	Eggs and adults	Mawirr	<i>Rottboellia exaltata</i> L.f.	Heading
<i>Nephotettix modulatus</i> Melichar	Nymphs	Mawirr	<i>R. exaltata</i>	Heading
			<i>Ischaemum rugosum</i> Salisb.	Heading
<i>Herpetogramma licarsialis</i> Walk.	Larvae	Rokupr mangrove swamp	<i>Paspalum vaginatum</i> Swartz	Vegetative
		Mawirr	<i>I. rugosum</i>	Heading
<i>Epilachna similis</i> Muls.	Nymphs and adults	Mawirr	<i>R. exaltata</i>	Heading
<i>Pteronemobius</i> sp.	Eggs	Mawirr	<i>R. exaltata</i>	Heading
<i>Hydrellia</i> sp.	Feeding lesions	Mange	<i>Pennisetum purpureum</i> Schumach.	Heading

Life span and tungro transmission of viruliferous *Nephotettix virescens*

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The rice tungro virus Collaborative Project investigated the life span and tungro transmission of *Nephotettix virescens*. In two trials in Thailand, 80 adult insects—40 females and 40 males—each for 10 varieties were given 4 days

access on tungro-diseased plants.

Transmission of the tungro virus was lowest in Gampai 30-12-15, Habiganj DW8, and Ambemohar 159, although these varieties were as susceptible to the hopper as TN1, based on life span.

Insect life spans ranged from 1 to 39 days, with an average of 7 days (7.5 for females and 6 for males). The short life spans on Pankhari 203 and Ptb 18 indicated that these varieties were more resistant than the others in the test. ■

Rice insect pests in Vietnam

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The pattern of incidence of insect pests in Vietnam has changed considerably since the introduction of high-yielding rice varieties and accompanying technology in 1968. Several minor insect pests have become major economic factors (see table).